

Formalization of Syntax and Semantics of Ontology Languages in Biology

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What is an ontology ?

A set of concepts and categories in a subject area or domain that shows their properties and the relations between them.

<https://www.lexico.com/en/definition/ontology>

<http://geneontology.org/docs/ontology-documentation/>

[Term]

id: GO:0019319

name: hexose biosynthetic process

namespace: biological_process

def: "The chemical reactions and pathways resulting in the formation of hexose." [ISBN:0198506732]

synonym: "hexose anabolism" EXACT []

synonym: "hexose biosynthesis" EXACT []

synonym: "hexose formation" EXACT []

synonym: "hexose synthesis" EXACT []

is_a: GO:0019318 ! hexose metabolic process

is_a: GO:0046364 ! monosaccharide biosynthetic process

The OBO Flat File Format Specification, version 1.2

john.richter@aya.yale.edu (John Day-Richter)

version 1.2, November 16, 2004

last revision: May 2nd, 2006

OBO format is the text file format used by [OBO-Edit](#), the open source, platform-independent application for viewing and editing ontologies. This replaces the previous [OBO 1.0 file format guide](#).

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- [Changes in version 1.2 and revision history](#)

https://owllcollab.github.io/oboformat/doc/GO.format.obo-1_2.html

OWL 2 Web Ontology Language Structural Specification and Functional-Style Syntax (Second Edition)

W3C Recommendation 11 December 2012

This version:

<http://www.w3.org/TR/2012/REC-owl2-syntax-20121211/>

Latest version (series 2):

<http://www.w3.org/TR/owl2-syntax/>

Latest Recommendation:

Endorsed By W3C

This document has been reviewed by W3C Members, by software developers, and by other W3C groups and interested parties, and is endorsed by the Director as a W3C Recommendation. It is a stable document and may be used as reference material or cited from another document. W3C's role in making the Recommendation is to draw attention to the specification and to promote its widespread deployment. This enhances the functionality and interoperability of the Web.

Conrad Bock, National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST)

[Achille Fokoue](#), IBM Corporation

[Peter Haase](#), FZI Research Center for Information Technology

[Rinke Hoekstra](#), University of Amsterdam

[Ian Horrocks](#), University of Oxford

[Alan Ruttenberg](#), Science Commons (Creative Commons)

[Uli Sattler](#), University of Manchester

[Michael Smith](#), Clark & Parsia

```

<owl:Class rdf:about="http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/G0_0019319">
  <rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/G0_0019318"/>
  <rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/G0_0046364"/>
  <obo:IAO_0000115 rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string">The chemical reactions are
  <oboInOwl:hasExactSynonym rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string">hexose anabolism
  <oboInOwl:hasExactSynonym rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string">hexose biosynthesis
  <oboInOwl:hasExactSynonym rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string">hexose formation
  <oboInOwl:hasExactSynonym rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string">hexose synthesis
  <oboInOwl:hasOBONamespace rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string">biological_process
  <oboInOwl:id rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string">G0:0019319</oboInOwl:id>
  <rdfs:label rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string">hexose biosynthetic process</rdfs:label>
</owl:Class>
<owl:Axiom>
  <owl:annotatedSource rdf:resource="http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/G0_0019319"/>
  <owl:annotatedProperty rdf:resource="http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/IAO_0000115"/>
  <owl:annotatedTarget rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string">The chemical reaction
  <oboInOwl:hasDbXref rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string">ISBN:0198506732</oboInOwl:hasDbXref>
</owl:Axiom>

```

Question

How to convert between OBO and OWL in a way that preserves the semantic content of the knowledge graph?

Table 2 OBO examples and corresponding OWL mappings

OBO	OWL
[Typedef] id: part_of name: part of is_transitive: true	<owl:TransitiveProperty rdf:about="#part_of"> <rdfs:label>part of</rdfs:label> </owl:TransitiveProperty>
<i>Example A Simple transformations: name, transitivity</i>	
[Term] id: ZFA:0000434 name: skeletal system is_a: ZFA:0001439	<owl:Class rdf:about="#ZFA_0000434"> <rdfs:label>skeletal system</rdfs:label> <rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="#ZFA_0001439"/> </owl:Class>
<i>Example B Transformation of 'is-a'</i>	
[Term] id: ZFA:0001439 name: anatomical system relationship: part_of ZFA:0001094	<owl:Class rdf:about="#ZFA_0001439"> <rdfs:label>anatomical system</rdfs:label> <rdfs:subClassOf><owl:Restriction> <owl:onProperty rdf:resource="#part_of" /> <owl:someValuesFrom rdf:resource="#ZFA_0001094" /> </owl:Restriction></rdfs:subClassOf> </owl:Class>
<i>Example C Transformation of a relationship</i>	
[Term] id: ZFA:0000437 name: stomach is_obsolete: true	<owl:Class rdf:about="&obolInOwl;ObsoleteClass"/> <owl:Class rdf:about="#ZFA_0000437"> <rdfs:label>stomach</rdfs:label> <rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="&obolInOwl;ObsoleteClass"/> </owl:Class>
<i>Example D Transformation of obsolete term</i>	

OBO examples in this table have been taken from ZFA.

Tirmizi, Syed Hamid, Stuart Aitken, Dilvan A. Moreira, Chris Mungall, Juan Sequeda, Nigam H. Shah, and Daniel P. Miranker. "Mapping between the OBO and OWL Ontology Languages." *Journal of Biomedical Semantics* 2, no. 1 (March 7, 2011): S3. doi:10.1186/2041-1480-2-S1-S3.

OBO 1.2 :

OBO Document Structure

An OBO document is structured as follows:

```
<header>  
  
<stanza>  
<stanza>  
...
```

Blank lines are ignored.

The header is an unlabeled section at the beginning of the document containing [tag-value pairs](#). The header ends when the first stanza is encountered.

A stanza is a labeled section of the document, indicating that an object of a particular type is being described. Stanzas consist of a stanza name in square brackets, and a series of [tag-value pairs](#), structured as follows:

```
[<Stanza name>  
<tag-value pair>  
<tag-value pair>  
<tag-value pair>
```

OBO 1.4 :

3.1 OBO Document Structure

An OBO document consists of a series of header frame followed by zero or more entity frames. Each frame has a set of clauses, or <tag,value> pairs. A tag is a token which may be drawn from the set of defined OBOF tags. The value can be atomic or multi-values. In the OBO Abstract syntax a clause is written <Tag>(<V1>...<Vn>).

Each frame should by convention be separated by an empty line, but this is not enforced in the syntax

Note that the term "frame" replaces the previously used "stanza" in order to be more consistent with Manchester Syntax.

```
OBO-Doc ::= header-frame { entity-frame } nl*  
entity-frame ::= term-frame | typedef-frame | Instance-frame
```

3.2 OBO Headers

```
header-frame ::= { header-clause nl* }  
header-clause ::= format-version-TVP  
| data-version-TVP  
| date-Tag DD:MM:YYYY ws hh:mm  
| saved-by-TVP  
| auto-generated-by-TVP  
| Import-Tag IRI | filepath  
| subsetdef-Tag Subset-ID ws QuotedString  
| svnonvmtvpedef-Tag SvnnonvmTvp-ID ws QuotedString
```

Question

**How to improve the OBO format
version 1.4 syntax?**

OBO 1.4 :

3.1 OBO Document Structure

An OBO document consists of a series of header frame followed by zero or more entity frames. Each frame has a set of clauses, or <tag,value> pairs. A tag is a token which may be drawn from the set of defined OBOF tags. The value can be atomic or multi-values. In the OBO Abstract syntax a clause is written <Tag>(<V1>...<Vn>).

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entity-frame ::= term-frame | typedef-frame | Instance-frame
```

3.2 OBO Headers

```
header-frame ::= { header-clause nl* }  
header-clause ::= format-version-TVP  
| data-version-TVP  
| date-Tag DD:MM:YYYY ws hh:mm  
| saved-by-TVP  
| auto-generated-by-TVP  
| Import-Tag IRI | filepath  
| subsetdef-Tag Subset-ID ws QuotedString  
| svnonvmtvpedef-Tag SvnnonvmTvp-ID ws QuotedString
```

```
// 3 Obo Grammar

// 3.1 Obo Document Structure

OboDoc      = { HeaderFrame ~ EntityFrame* ~ EOI }
EntityFrame = { TermFrame | InstanceFrame | TypedefFrame }
HeaderClause = {
    FormatVersionTag ~ UnquotedString
  | DataVersionTag ~ UnquotedString
  | DateTag ~ NaiveDateTime
  | SavedByTag ~ UnquotedString
  | AutoGeneratedByTag ~ UnquotedString
  | ImportTag ~ Import
  | SubsetdefTag ~ SubsetId ~ QuotedString
  | SynonymTypedefTag ~ SynonymTypeId ~ QuotedString ~ SynonymScope?
  | DefaultNamespaceTag ~ NamespaceId
  | IdspaceTag ~ IdPrefix ~ Iri ~ QuotedString?
```


crates.io

Rust Package Registry

Click or press 'S' to search...

[Browse All Crates](#)

[Docs](#)

Martin Larraalde

fastobo-syntax 0.3.3

Follow

[Homepage](#) [Documentation](#) [Repository](#) [Dependent crates](#)

Cargo.toml

```
fastobo-syntax = "0.3.3"
```


fastobo-syntax

Star 1

PEG Syntax and pest parser for the OBO flat file format 1.4

build passing coverage 100% license MIT source GitHub crates.io v0.3.3 docs.rs latest

keep a changelog issues 0 open

Last Updated

a month ago

issue resolution 0 s

maintenance actively-developed

build passing

Crate Size

11.67 kB

Module ast

Structs

Enums

Traits

Type Definitions

fastobo

Modules

ast

error

Click or press 'S' to search, '?' for more options...

Module fastobo::ast

[-][src]

[-] Owned syntax tree for the [OBO format version 1.4](#).

[OboDoc](#) is the struct acting as the root of the syntax tree. It can be created from a borrowed string slice with either [FromStr::from_str](#) or [FromSlice::from_slice](#), from a file with [fastobo::from_file](#), or from a buffered reader with [fastobo::from_stream](#).

Structs

ClassId	A borrowed ClassIdent .
ClassIdent	A unique identifier for a class (<i>i.e.</i> a term).
Comment	An inline comment without semantic value.
HeaderFrame	The header frame, containing metadata about an OBO document.
IdLocal	A borrowed IdLocal .
IdPrefix	A borrowed IdentPrefix
IdentLocal	A local identifier, preceded by a prefix in prefixed IDs.
IdentPrefix	An identifier prefix. either canonical or non-canonical.

Question

How many OBO ontologies are actually valid?

Download table as: [[YAML](#) | [JSON-LD](#) | [RDF/Turtle](#)]

bfo	Basic Formal Ontology 									
chebi	Chemical Entities of Biological Interest 									
doid	Human Disease Ontology 									
go	Gene Ontology 									
obi	Ontology for Biomedical Investigations 									
pato	Phenotype And Trait Ontology 									
po	Plant Ontology 									
pr	PRotein Ontology (PRO) 									

An ontology for describing the function of genes and gene products

 Follow @news4go 1,806 followers

[OntoBee](#)
[AberOWL](#)
[OLS](#)
[AmiGO](#)

The goal of the GeneOntology (GO) project is to provide a uniform way to describe the functions of gene products from organisms across all kingdoms of life and thereby enable analysis of genomic data

Products

go.owl	GO (OWL edition)	The main ontology in OWL. This is self contained and does not have connections to other OBO ontologies [page]
go.obo	GO (OBO Format edition)	Equivalent to go.owl, in obo format [page]
go.json	GO (JSON edition)	Equivalent to go.owl, in obograph json format [page]
go/extensions/go-plus.owl	GO-Plus	The main ontology plus axioms connecting to select external ontologies [page]
go/extensions/go-plus.json	GO-Plus	As go-plus.owl, in obographs json format [page]
go/go-basic.obo	GO-Basic, Filtered, for use with legacy tools	The main ontology plus axioms connecting to select external ontologies [page]
go/go-basic.json	GO-Basic, Filtered, for use with legacy tools (JSON)	As go-basic.obo, in json format [page]

ID Space [go](#)
PURL [http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/go.owl](#)
License [CC BY 4.0](#)
Homepage [http://geneontology.org/](#)
Contact [Suzi Aleksander](#)
Trackers [https://github.com/geneontology/geneontology/issues/biology](#)
Domain [http://go.termgenie.org](#)
TermGenie
Taxon [All life](#)
Dependencies [uberon](#)
[cl](#)
[ncbitaxon](#)
[ro](#)
[go/extensions/go-bridge-to-nifstd.owl](#)

[View](#)
[Edit](#)
[PURL](#)

Generated by: [_layouts/ontology_detail.html](#)
See [metadata guide](#)

Edit the metadata for this page: [go.md](#) (GitHub will help you create a fork and pull request.)

Count of invalid OBO products in the OBO foundry

OBO 1.4 compliance for OBO Foundry ontologies

Updated 6 days ago

Filter cards

+ Add cards

Fullscreen

To do	In progress	Waiting release	Done	No work needed
HOM Invalid xrefs Line 153, col 23 xref: MeSH:Structural Homology\ Protein Added by althonos	ENVO EnvironmentOntology/envo/pull/747 Added by althonos 1 Reference [WIP] OBO format version 1.4 compliance 12 of 23 #747 opened by althonos in EnvironmentOntology/envo bug enhancement Changes approved	SYMP Invalid dbxrefs Added by althonos 1 Reference Invalid syntax in `symp.obo` #4 opened by althonos in DiseaseOntology/SymptomOntology	BSPO Invalid dbxref Added by althonos 1 Reference Fix xref ID in `bspo-edit.obo` #14 opened by althonos in obophenotype/biological-spatial-ontology	APO Added by althonos
FIX Outdated syntax xref_analog: line 18, col 1 xref_analog: ISBN:0471988631 Added by althonos	ECOCORE Invalid ISBN identifier format ENVO derived error (invalid ISBN in xref): line 7434, col 339 ... ISBN:0030584140 9780030584145 Added by althonos	UBERON Invalid dbxref Added by althonos 1 Reference OBO 1.4 syntax and Quality-of-Life improvements 9 of 17 #1496 opened by althonos in obophenotype/uberon Changes approved	MI Invalid xrefs Invalid placeholder in dbxref ID Added by althonos 2 References	CIO Added by althonos
GAZ Invalid xref ID: line 528, col 11 xref: YNP RCN Geothermal Features Database:NPB150 Added by althonos			ECO Invalid ISO-8601 dates Invalid header date Added by althonos	BFO Added by althonos
CHEBI				CEPH Added by althonos
				DDANAT Added by althonos
				DDPHENO Added by althonos

[WIP] OBO format version 1.4 compliance #747

Edit

Merged cmungall merged 12 commits into EnvironmentOntology:master from unknown repository on Apr 13

Conversation 4

Commits 12

Checks 0

Files changed 2

+151 -151

althonos commented on Apr 6 • edited

Contributor + 😊 ...

Required

- Fix qualifiers in Xref lists (mainly for definitions)
 - Figure out what to do with identifier written Adapted from ... : possibly use trailing qualifiers ?
 - Figure out what to do with accessed : trailing qualifier ?
 - Replace IRBAS working group (CESAB) with URL or citation reference ?
 - Replace EuPath team simply with URL ?
 - Add Ruth's ORCID instead of Ruth's ORCID 😊
 - Add sources to ENV0:01001498 or remove the current Xrefs
- Replace references to books with their ISBN:
 - Glossary of Environment Statistics: ISBN:9211613868
 - MGH Encyclopedia of Scientific and Technical Terms: ISBN:9780070452589
 - McGraw-Hill Dictionary of Architecture and Construction.: ISBN:9780071452373
 - Food, Cuisine and Society in Prehistoric Greece: ISBN:9781842171677
 - Collected Papers from the 18th Biennial Mogollon Archaeology Conference: ISBN:9780989317412
 - Methods for collecting, preserving, and studying insects and allied forms: ISBN:9780646045696
 - Ecological Methods With Particular Reference to the Study of Insect Populations: ISBN:9789400912250
- Replace references to papers with an identifier:
 - Barber H (1931) Traps for cave-inhabiting insects: ???
 - Hertz M (1927) Huomioita petokuoriaisten olinpaikoista: ???
 - Mitchell B (1963) Ecology of two carabid beetles: DOI:10.2307/2599
 - Luetscher, M & Jeannin, P-Y (2004): "A process-based classification of alpine ice caves." ???

Suggested

- Standardize format for ISBN ? GO xrefs expect ISBN:XXXXXXXXX but "official" format has separated digit groups (e.g. ISBN:XXX-X-XXXX-XXXX-X).
- Standardize format for ISO norms ?
- Standardize GEMET identifiers ? Should probably be either a plain URL or a GEMET:XXXX id, currently is GEMET:<URL> .

Reviewers

cmungall ✓

Assignees

No one assigned

Labels

bug
enhancement

Projects

Done in betterTech

Milestone

No milestone

Notifications Customize

Unsubscribe

You're receiving notifications because you were mentioned.

3 participants

Question

**How to prevent invalid OBO products
from being released?**

ontology-development-kit

build failing

Initialize a Git repo for managing your ontology the OBO Library way!

For more details, see

- [2018 Article](#)
- [ICBO Workshop Slides 2018](#)
- [ICBO Workshop Slides 2017](#)

/tmp fastobo-validator xlmod.obo

Wed 28 Aug 2019 22:37:58 CEST

Parsing `xlmod.obo`

Failed parsing `xlmod.obo`

--> xlmod.obo:730:37

730 | property_value: base specificities: "(Guanine)" xsd:string^{LF}
| ^_ _ _

= expected EOL or XsdDatatype

/tmp fastobo-validator poro.obo

Tue 23 Jul 2019 15:28:17 UTC

Parsing `poro.obo`

Finished parsing `poro.obo` in 0.03s

Failed validation of `poro.obo` (13 errors)

--> in frame adjacent_to
duplicate "def" clauses--> in frame produced_by
duplicate "name" clauses--> in frame continuous_with
duplicate "name" clauses

Question

**How to improve the semantic mappings
for the OBO language?**

OBO ecosystem: an overview

Question

How to improve support for ontologies in Python?

fastobo 0.3.1


```
pip install fastobo
```


Last released: Aug 8, 2019

Faultless AST for Open Biomedical Ontologies in Python.

Navigation

Project description

Release history

Download files

Project links

Homepage

Documentation

Changelog

Bug Reports

Project description

fastobo-py **3**

Faultless AST for Open Biomedical Ontologies in Python.

build **passing** license **MIT** source **GitHub** pypi **v0.3.1** wheel **yes** python **3.5 | 3.6 | 3.7** implementation **cpython**
keep a **changelog** docs **passing** issues **0 open**

Overview

`fastobo` is a Rust library implementing a reliable parser for the OBO file format 1.4. This extension module exports idiomatic Python bindings that can be used to load, edit and serialize ontologies in the OBO format.

Installation

```
>>> from urllib.request import urlopen
>>> import fastobo
>>> for frame in fastobo.load(urlopen("http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/cl.obo")):
...     for clause in frame:
...         if clause.raw_key == "def" and not clause.definition:
...             print("Empty definition of", frame.id)
```

An example script using the Python API

Use `fastobo` to load ontologies from OBO files #360

Edit

Open althonos wants to merge 2 commits into biolink:master from althonos:feat-fastobo

Conversation 3

Commits 2

Checks 0

Files changed 3

+12 -2

althonos commented 20 days ago

+ 😊 ...

Hi !

This PR (finally) adds a native OBO parser using the `fastobo` package. This is very much WIP since there are no actual semantics for OBO to OBO Graphs translation, and the translation is in early development.

I added it in a way `fastobo` becomes a mandatory dependency, which is not optimal on platforms other than Linux and OSX x86-64 since it requires a Rust toolchain to be available on the target machine; I could make it optional as well if you think this is better.

Reviewers

- cmungall
- dougli1sqrd
- deepakunni3

Assignees

No one assigned

Labels

None yet

Projects

None yet

althonos and others added some commits 20 days ago

Use `fastobo` to load ontologies from OBO files

✓ ad1aebc

Merge branch 'master' into feat-fastobo

Verified ✓ a510e92

Results

[OK] Improved OBO 1.4 Syntax and Semantics

[OK] Strict OBO Parser Implementation

[OK] Accurate OBO Syntax Tree

[OK] OBO Foundry Ecosystem Validation

[OK] Ontology Development Kit Integration

[OK] Python Wrapper

[WIP] OBO to OWL Restricted Mapping

[WIP] OBO to/from OBO Graphs Mapping

Conclusion

- Full implementation of the OBO 1.4 specification
- Identified several bugs in the OWL API
- Identified spurious annotations in released OBO products
- Served as a solid basis to the development of a new semantic stack in Rust
- Is to be used as a backend parser in Python libraries for *ontobio* and *pronto*

Final Words

- Poster presented at BOSC 2019 (part of ISMB/ECCB 2019):
<https://f1000research.com/posters/8-1500>
- I would like to thank
 - **Chris Mungall** and all members of the **BBOP** team
 - **Phillip Lord** for his work on the OWL2 model in Rust
- *Any questions?*